

Quantitative phytochemical analysis of *Achyranthes aspera*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Cissus quadrangularis* and *Mimosa pudica* from the Ramgarh Block of Ramgarh District, Jharkhand

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a quantitative comparison of major phytochemical classes in four medicinal plants- *Achyranthes aspera*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Cissus quadrangularis* and *Mimosa pudica* collected from the different places of Ramgarh block, Ramgarh district, Jharkhand, India. Using standardized extraction (70% methanol) and established spectrophotometric assays, we determined total phenolic content (TPC; mg GAE/g extract), total flavonoid content (TFC; mg QE/g extract), and concentrations/percentages of alkaloids, and tannins. *Tinospora cordifolia* showed the highest TPC and TFC, while *Achyranthes aspera* had appreciable saponin content. Significant interspecific differences ($p < 0.001$) were observed across assays. Results provide a phytochemical baseline for these species in the Ramgarh region and inform future pharmacological and conservation work.

Key Words - *Achyranthes aspera*, *Tinospora cordifolia*, *Cissus quadrangularis*, *Mimosa pudica*, total phenolics, total flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are a central part of traditional healthcare systems worldwide; their therapeutic potential is primarily driven by classes of secondary metabolites such as phenolics, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins and tannins (Harborne, 1998; Singleton & Rossi, 1965). Quantitative phytochemical profiling is essential for assessing medicinal value, guiding pharmacological screening, and supporting conservation and sustainable use strategies (Chang *et al.*, 2002; Obadoni & Ochuko, 2001).

The selected species-*Achyranthes aspera* (Family- Amaranthaceae), *Tinospora cordifolia* (Family- Menispermaceae), *Cissus quadrangularis* (Family- Vitaceae) and *Mimosa pudica* (Family- Fabaceae)- are used in folk medicine for a variety of indications

including anti-inflammatory, wound healing, analgesic and digestive disorders (Hayatou *et al.*, 2023; Praveen & Rajesh, 2018; Talreja *et al.*, 2017). Despite their ethnobotanical importance, comparative quantitative data from specific geographic regions such as Ramgarh block (Ramgarh district, Jharkhand, India) are scarce. Local edaphic and climatic conditions can influence secondary metabolite profiles; therefore region-specific data are valuable (CI & Indira, 2016; Muhammad *et al.*, 2020; Okah & Cornelius, 2019).

This study aimed to quantify TPC (Total Phenolic Content), TFC (Total Flavonoid Content), alkaloids, saponins and tannins in methanolic extracts of the four species collected from Ramgarh block, providing baseline data and interspecies

comparison (Patel *et al.*, 2014; Sankhlar & Vernekar, 2016; Shaikh & Patil, 2020).

MATERIALS & METHODS

Sample collection and identification

Aerial parts (leaves and stems were traditionally used) of *Mimosa pudica*, stem and roots of *Achyranthus aspera* and stems of *Tinospora cordifolia* and *Cissus quadrangularis* were collected from multiple sites within Ramgarh block, Ramgarh district, Jharkhand, India. Plants were identified by an experienced local vaidya, Pahan and Bhagat.

Preparation of extracts

Samples were washed, shade-dried at room temperature and powdered. For each species, 10 g of powdered material was subjected to cold maceration with 100 mL of 70% methanol for 48 h with occasional shaking. Extracts were filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentrated under reduced pressure at 40°C using a rotary evaporator and then lyophilized to obtain dry extract. Extract yields (w/w) were recorded.

All assays were performed on extracts dissolved in methanol at required concentrations. All measurements were conducted in triplicate (n = 3 independent extractions/assays).

Quantitative assays

Total phenolic content (TPC)

The total phenolic content (TPC) of the dried extracts was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu method. An aliquot of 1 ml of extract (1 mg/ml) was mixed with 1 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After allowing the reaction to stand for 5 minutes, 10 ml of 7% sodium carbonate solution was added, followed by the addition of 13 ml of deionized distilled water. The mixture was vortexed thoroughly and incubated in the dark for 90 minutes at 23°C. The absorbance of the resulting solution was then measured at 760 nm.

The phenolic content was calculated using a calibration curve generated from standard gallic acid solutions. All measurements were performed in triplicate. The TPC was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of dried extract.

Total flavonoid content (TFC)

The quantitative estimation of total flavonoid content was carried out by pipetting 0.25 mL of the plant extract into a test tube, followed by dilution with 1.25 mL of distilled water. Subsequently, 0.75 mL of 5% sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) solution was added, mixed thoroughly, and the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 minutes. Then, 0.15 mL of 10% aluminium chloride (AlCl_3) solution was added, and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 6 minutes. After this, 0.5 mL of 1N sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added, and the final volume was adjusted by adding 0.275 mL of distilled water. The absorbance of the resulting solution was measured at 510 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer

Alkaloid Content (Subramanian, 2024)

A volume of 1.2 mL of each fruit and seed extract sample was taken. To this, 2.5 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 4.7) was added in a test tube. Subsequently, 2.5 mL of Bromocresol Green (BCG) solution was added and mixed thoroughly. A total of 5 mL of chloroform (in two portions: 2 mL followed by 3 mL) was added to the mixture. After each addition, the mixture was shaken well and filtered.

The filtrate was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark using chloroform. Accurately measured aliquots of 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, and 1.2 $\mu\text{L}/\text{mL}$ were taken for preparing the atropine standard curve. The standard atropine solution was prepared at a concentration of 1 mg/10 mL (dry weight basis).

The absorbance of both the standard atropine solutions and the sample extracts was recorded at 470 nm against a blank. All measurements were carried out in triplicate to ensure accuracy.

Tannin content

The total tannin content was quantified using the Folin-Ciocalteu method. For the analysis, 0.1 ml of the plant extract was transferred into a 10 ml volumetric flask containing 7.5 ml of distilled water, followed by the addition of 0.5 ml of Folin-Ciocalteu phenol reagent. Subsequently, 1 ml of 35% sodium carbonate solution was added, and the volume was

made up to 10 ml with distilled water. The mixture was thoroughly shaken and incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes.

Standard solutions of tannic acid (20, 40, 60, 80 and 100 µg/ml) were prepared using the same procedure. The absorbance of the test samples and standards was recorded at 700 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer, with distilled water serving as the blank.

All measurements were performed in triplicate. The tannin concentration was expressed as milligrams of tannic acid equivalents per gram of dried plant material.

RESULTS

Extract yield

Approximate extract yields (70% methanol, w/w on dry material) were: *Tinospora cordifolia* 15.8%, *Achyranthus aspera* 12.4%, *Cissus quadrangularis* 10.2%, *Mimosa pudica* 8.1%.

Table 1: Preparation of calibration curve of Gallic acid

Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance at (760nm)
0	0.45
20	1.101
40	1.358
60	1.469
80	1.695
100	1.891

Figure 1: Gallic acid standard curve

Table 2- Preparation of calibration curve of Quercetin

Concentration(µg/ml)	Absorbance at 510nm
0	0.056
100	0.112
200	0.136
400	0.204
600	0.303
800	0.331
1000	0.392

Figure 2 : Quercetin standard curve

Table 3- Preparation of calibration curve of Tannic acid

Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance at 700nm
0	0.048
20	0.283
40	0.432
60	0.623
80	0.808
100	0.990

Figure 3: Tannic acid standard curve

Table 4- Preparation of calibration curve of Atropine curve

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance at 470nm
0	0.197
0.4	0.256
0.6	0.301
0.8	0.343
1	0.396
1.2	0.401

Figure 4: Atropine standard curve

DISCUSSION

This comparative phytochemical screening indicates substantial interspecific variation in major secondary metabolite classes among the four medicinal plants collected from Ramgarh block.

Tinospora cordifolia displayed the highest TPC and TFC whereas *Achyranthes aspera* showed the lowest TPC and TFC. Alkaloid levels were highest in *T. cordifolia* and *A. aspera*, which may relate to observed bioactivities (analgesic, antipyretic).

Cissus quadrangularis and *Mimosa pudica* had comparatively lower phenolic and flavonoid contents; however, these species are known for specific bioactive compounds (e.g., vitamin C, carotenoids, triterpenoids, and unique alkaloids) that may not be fully captured by broad spectrophotometric assays.

Geographic and seasonal factors, plant part selection, and extraction solvent strongly influence secondary metabolite yields. The use of 70% methanol provides a broad extraction spectrum but selective solvents could reveal different profiles. Therefore, while the present data provide a

baseline, targeted chromatographic analyses (HPLC, LC-MS) are recommended to identify individual compounds.

CONCLUSION

Quantitative phytochemical profiling of *A. aspera*, *T. cordifolia*, *C. quadrangularis* and *M. pudica* from Ramgarh block shows that *T. cordifolia* is particularly rich in phenolics, flavonoids and tannins, while *A. aspera* is notable for saponins. Significant interspecies variation was observed for all tested phytochemical classes ($p < 0.001$). These data form a local phytochemical baseline that supports focused pharmacological testing and conservation planning. Researchers and practitioners should consider geographic variability when sourcing plant material for therapeutic or research purposes.

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